

Preparing the Nuclear Workforce of Tomorrow

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803353

ABSTRACT

The American Nuclear Society (ANS) is helping to meet the current and future needs of the nuclear workforce by launching a new Certified Nuclear Professional (CNP) credential and by developing a new professional development certificate course program. These initiatives will supplement traditional nuclear science and engineering education delivered by universities, community colleges, and trade schools. As demand for nuclear increases across the world, so does the need for skilled workers in the industry. The overall goal of these programs is to provide education and learning opportunities for individuals looking to enter the field as well as those currently in the field who are interested in expanding their nuclear knowledge. ANS is well on its way to achieving this goal with the launch of the CNP credential in 2025 and by continuing to expand its certificate course offerings. This paper and presentation will provide detailed information about the programs and how they will help prepare the nuclear workforce of tomorrow.

Keywords: Workforce, education, certification, credential, development

1. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear energy industry is undergoing a major workforce transformation on two primary fronts; first, current staff knowledge gaps are becoming more evident as one generation retires, while a less experienced generation makes up the remaining workforce. Second, large investments in the development of advanced nuclear fission plants and advanced nuclear fuels have resulted in a projected need for an additional 375,000 nuclear industry employees by 2050. These factors have resulted in near-term large-scale recruitment of non-nuclear professionals to fill expanding immediate workforce needs.

The American Nuclear Society has taken up the challenge to set the standard for nuclear industry professionals by developing a professional credentials program to support the workforce of the future. To this end, the ANS President's Special Committee on Certification was created to investigate the ways the Society can help broaden the pool of qualified potential candidates available to fill the growing number of employer vacancies across the nuclear industry. Committee efforts were initiated in June 2022 following approval by the ANS Board of Directors to conduct a market analysis and provide recommendations via a report to the Board in June 2023. Subject matter expertise and leadership were provided by ANS volunteers, ANS staff, and consultants that specialize in the development of certification and credentialing programs for technical professionals.

After conducting six months of market research, the President's Special Committee on Certification recommended that ANS take a two-pronged approach to address the identified immediate workforce gaps. First, the development of a certificate program for specialized technical topics. Each certificate requires completion of a course, related activities, or experiences and ends with an examination. And second, the establishment of a professional certification, the Certified Nuclear Professional (CNP)

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credential, which requires a longer-term commitment ending with an examination and requiring continuing education activities to maintain the designation.

2. ABOUT THE PROGRAMS

2.1. Certified Nuclear Professional Credential

The Certified Nuclear Professional (CNP) credential establishes industry standards and serves as a comprehensive measure of knowledge in the field. The CNP designation distinguishes nuclear professionals who have met an established standard of knowledge and understanding of nuclear fundamentals. The designation also provides employers and the public with the assurance that certified individuals possess the necessary job skills, knowledge, and experience in the nuclear field to perform their duties competently.

Led by the ANS Special Committee on Certification, the development of the program was a two-year long process that culminated with the launch of the CNP exam during the summer of 2025. Including members of the Committee, more than 30 subject matter experts covering a broad range of nuclear topic areas were involved in the development of the exam.

The exam development process consisted of four phases: Job task analysis, item writing, exam form review and finalization, and cut score and standard setting. The job task analysis involved establishing a subject matter expert team to help outline the knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) that define a minimally competent generalist/specialist professional in the nuclear field. A comprehensive survey of ANS members and nuclear professionals was then conducted to refine the KSAs. Following an analysis of the survey findings, the CNP exam specifications were developed. The specifications feature eight domains: Applied Health Physics, Fuel Cycle and Waste Management, General Nuclear Safety Culture, Industry Codes and Standards, Licensing and Regulatory Concepts, Non-Power Applications of Radiation & Nuclear Technology, Nuclear Fundamentals, and Nuclear Power.

For the second phase, item writing, a new subject matter expert team was assembled with some overlap with the job task analysis team. This group, along with a psychometrician, conducted a comprehensive needs analysis to determine the number of exam questions needed per subject domain. This provided a more detailed exam outline that the item writers used to develop a bank of questions for the CNP exam.

The third step of the CNP development process included a thorough review and beta testing period. Another subject matter expert team was assembled to take the exam and review it in detail for technical accuracy while a psychometrician reviewed it to ensure that the exam is defensible.

The final phase concluded the development of the exam by setting the cut score, which is the threshold that separates examinees who pass from examinees who fail based on the minimum competence required to perform as a professional in the nuclear industry.

2.1.1. Who should take the CNP exam?

The CNP certification is recommended for individuals who have at least two years of professional experience in the nuclear industry and are seeking to validate their knowledge and commitment to excellence in the field. The certification is well-suited for early- to mid-career professionals working in areas such as nuclear operations, regulatory compliance, quality assurance, safety, or project management.

2.1.2. Eligibility requirements

CNP candidates must meet the following requirements:

1. Hold a high school diploma or GED equivalent as a minimum AND
2. Demonstrate completion of nuclear education or work experience; this includes

- Two (2) years of nuclear on-the-job work experience OR
- Eighty (80) hours of continuing professional education that is offered by any professional entity if the education is directly related to the domains covered by the CNP exam OR
- Two (2) years of nuclear education completed at an associate-degree level or above. Alternative options to fulfill the nuclear education requirement could include the following:
- Possession of a Senior Reactor Operator (SRO) License or Reactor Operator (RO) license,
- Completion of the U.S. Navy's Nuclear Power School (enlisted or officer) or operator training at a prototype school, or
- Other forms of nuclear education or coursework.

2.1.3. About the exam

Once a candidates' application has been approved, demonstrating that they meet the eligibility requirements, they must take the CNP exam through a Pearson VUE in-person testing center. The exam consists of 100 questions and candidates have 2 hours and 30 minutes to complete this exam. A variety of question types are used including single-answer, multiple choice; multiple-answer multiple choice; matching; or drag-and-drop type. Each question is equally weighted; the answer is either fully correct or incorrect.

2.1.4. Recertification requirements

Certified Nuclear Professionals must recertify to ensure continued competence through the ongoing development of knowledge and skills in the nuclear field. The process reinforces a commitment to professional growth, safety, regulatory awareness, and evolving industry practices. All CNPs are required to renew their certification every three years by meeting the following recertification requirements:

- Complete 36 hours of continuing education (CE) relevant to the CNP body of knowledge during the 3-year certification period; and
- Submit a renewal application and pay the required fee
- Reaffirm adherence to the ANS Code of Ethics and Respectful Behavior Policy

2.2 Nuclear 101 Certificate Course

The new Certificate Course program launched in 2024 with the debut of the Nuclear 101 Certificate Course. The program sold out in weeks, prompting ANS to add additional in-person offerings during its national conferences in 2025. An online version will soon be available to help reach even more professionals and students looking to enhance their understanding of nuclear science, as well as individuals new to the industry. The 4.5-day course includes 32 hours of in-class time plus 8 hours of pre-course work.

The Nuclear 101 course is designed to quickly get students up-to-speed and provide foundational knowledge to help them succeed in careers in the nuclear industry, whether they're already in the field or are looking to join the nuclear workforce.

The course's 12 modules cover a vast array of topics, including History and Legacy of Nuclear, Nuclear Fundamentals, Introduction to Nuclear Fuel Cycle, Nuclear Reactors and Power Generation, Licensing and Regulatory Concepts, Radiation Detection and Measurement, Health Physics and Radiation Safety, Non-Power Applications of Nuclear Energy, Nuclear Safety Culture, and Advanced Reactor Technologies.

In addition to in-person offerings, the course will be available as a self-paced, online program in 2026.

2.3 Nuclear Licensing & Regulation Certificate Course

The Nuclear Licensing & Regulation Certificate Course is a 16-hour self-paced, online program for industry professionals with existing nuclear knowledge, especially those in operations, engineering,

communications, or oversight. The course examines the unique regulatory practices of the nuclear industry to help nuclear professionals prepare for roles requiring regulatory knowledge.

Course modules include US Nuclear Regulatory Commission, US Department of Energy, US Environmental Protection Agency, Nuclear Regulatory Governance, Types of NRC Licenses, Safety Analysis Reports, Technical Specification and Bases, Licensing Change Processes, Reactor Oversight Process, Fuel Licensing Considerations, Transportation, Waste Management, Decommissioning Regulations, and International Regulatory Framework.

2.4 Radioactive Waste Management Certificate Course

The Radioactive Waste Management Certificate Course was designed for employers, professionals, and students looking to establish a foundational understanding and common vocabulary of nuclear waste management topics. Students learn about topics such as key metrics of radioactive waste across the fuel cycle, history of nuclear waste management, U.S. and IAEA radioactive waste classification systems, waste storage, conditioning, transportation, and disposal technologies for each waste type, performance assessments and safety for radioactive waste disposal, regulations surrounding hazardous waste management, and spent nuclear fuel recycling and its economic and environmental impacts.

The course debuted in November 2025 and an online version is planned for late 2026.

3. ABOUT THE AMERICAN NUCLEAR SOCIETY

Established in 1954, the American Nuclear Society is an international professional organization of engineers, scientists, technologists, teachers, and healthcare providers devoted to the peaceful applications of nuclear science and technology. Its more than 12,000 members represent government, academia, research laboratories, medical facilities, and private industry. ANS's mission is to empower a strong, connected, and engaged professional community that cultivates nuclear science and technology for the benefit of humanity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The American Nuclear Society's efforts to prepare the nuclear workforce of tomorrow is only just beginning. While the Certified Nuclear Professional is now fully launched, ANS is investing significant resources to increase awareness of the credential among individuals and the organizations that will be growing their own workforces in the years ahead. Similarly, the Society is working to rapidly expand its professional development certificate course catalog, with plans to add several courses each year, including the introduction of a Business of Nuclear Economics course and a series of nuclear safety cultures in 2026. ANS also plans to continue building upon the many partnerships with allied organizations throughout the nuclear industry to work together to ensure the nuclear field is equipped to meet the rising demand for nuclear technology in the years ahead.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the ANS Certification and Workforce Development Committee, including Chair Rebecca Steinman, and past members of the ANS Special Committee on Certification, including ANS Past President Steven Arndt, who established the committee. The authors would also like to thank the many volunteers who have contributed countless hours to the development of the Certified Nuclear Professional credential and the Certificate Courses.